

Enhancement of Cloud Security through Two Level Cryptographic Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Cloud Computing is a set of IT Services. It has various characteristics like scalability, elasticity, multi-tenancy, pay-per-use approach make cloud computing the popular paradigm today. It is adopted by various organizations and by governments nowadays. Despite the potential gains achieved from the cloud computing, the organizations are slow in accepting it due to its security issues and challenges associated with it. In this research paper, the proposed work plan is to provide two level cryptographic algorithms to enhance the security in cloud. This algorithm is useful in transmission of messages and data in the cloud.

Keywords:

Cloud Computing, Cryptography, Decryption, Encryption, Symmetric, Asymmetric

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing is the delivery of computing services over the Internet. Cloud computing [1] can be defined as a way of providing IT resources in the form of computing infrastructure, storage, networking, computing application to consumers as services using Internet at any time whenever they are required. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) special publication (2011) defined Cloud computing as a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction [2]. Because of these benefits each and every organizations are moving their data to the cloud. So there is a need to protect that data against unauthorized access, modification or denial of services etc.. Security goals of data include three points namely: Availability Confidentiality, and Integrity. Confidentiality of data in the cloud is accomplished by cryptography. Cryptography, in modern days is considered combination of three types of algorithms. They are (i) Symmetric-key algorithms (ii) Asymmetric-key algorithms and (ii) Hashing.

(i) **Symmetric-key algorithms** :- With secret key cryptography, a single key is used for both encryption and decryption. As shown in Figure 1, the sender uses the key

(or some set of rules) to encrypt the plaintext and sends the cipher text to the receiver. The receiver applies the same key (or rule set) to decrypt the message and recover the plaintext. Because a single key is used for both functions, secret key cryptography is also called symmetric encryption. Example Data Encryption Standard (DES), Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), International Data Encryption Algorithm (IDEA), Blowfish, Camellia, SEED

(ii) **Asymmetric-key algorithms**: - Generic PKC employs two keys that are mathematically related although knowledge of one key does not allow someone to easily determine the other key. One key is used to encrypt the plaintext and the other key is used to decrypt the cipher text. The important point here is that it does not matter which key is applied first, but that both keys are required for the process to work (Figure 2). Because a pair of keys is required, this approach is also called asymmetric cryptography. Example: RSA, Diffie-Hellman, Digital Signature Algorithm (DSA), and Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC)

(iii) **Hash Function**: - Hash functions, also called message digests and one-way encryption, are algorithms that, in some sense, use no key. Instead, a fixed-length hash value is computed based upon the plaintext that makes it impossible for either the contents or length of the plaintext to be recovered. Hash algorithms are typically used to provide a *digital fingerprint* of a file's contents often used to ensure that the file has not been altered by an intruder or virus. Hash functions are also commonly employed by many operating systems to encrypt passwords. Hash functions, then, provide a measure of the integrity of a file. Example Message Digest (MD) algorithms, Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA), HAVAL (HASH of VARIABLE Length), Whirlpool, Tiger etc.

Hash functions, for example, are well-suited for ensuring data integrity because any change made to the contents of a message will result in the receiver calculating a different hash value than the one placed in the transmission by the sender. Since it is highly unlikely that two different messages will yield the same hash value, data integrity is ensured to a high degree of confidence. Secret key cryptography, on the other hand, is ideally suited to encrypting messages, thus providing privacy and confidentiality. The sender can generate a session key on a

per-message basis to encrypt the message; the receiver, of course, needs the same session key to decrypt the message. Key exchange, of course, is a key application of public-key cryptography. Asymmetric schemes can also be used for non-repudiation and user authentication; if the receiver can obtain the session key encrypted with the sender's private key, then only this sender could have sent the message. Public-key cryptography could, theoretically, also be used to encrypt messages although this is rarely done because secret-key cryptography operates about 1000 times faster than public-key cryptography.

To encrypt data at cloud storage both symmetric-key and asymmetric-key algorithms can be used. Cloud storage contains a large set of databases and for such a large database asymmetric-key algorithm's performance is slower when compared to symmetric-key algorithms

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Cloud computing has been defined by US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [3] as "a model for enabling convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or cloud provider interaction". The NIST definition is one of the clearest and most comprehensive definitions of cloud computing and is widely referenced in US government documents and projects.

Brian Hay et. al [4] has focused on data authentication, data integrity, querying and outsourcing the encrypted data. Their research says that, the risks can arise at operational trust modes, resource sharing, new attack strategies. In operational trust modes, the encrypted communication channels are used for cloud storage and do the computation on encrypted data which is called as homomorphic encryption [5]. New attack strategies like Virtual Machine Introspection (VMI) can be used at virtualization layer to process and alter the data.

In [6, 7] the authors examined different security and privacy concerns related to cloud computing. They discussed and outlined the risks, their influences, and the opportunities. Adequate levels of reliability, confidentiality, and sensitive data protection are examples of many security concerns [8].

Kevin Curran et.al [9] mentions that Cloud Computing is a distributed architecture that centralizes server resources on a scalable platform so as to provide on demand computing resources and services. Cloud computing has become a variable platform for companies to build their infrastructures upon. If companies are to consider taking advantage of cloud based systems by storing their data in

Cloud Storage they will be faced with the task of seriously reassessing their current security strategy.

Randeep Kaur et.al [10] mentions some of the notable challenges associated with cloud Storage. The challenges are Security, Privacy and Lack of Standards which slow down services in the cloud.

Rashmi Nigoti et.al [11] defines some privacy and security-related issues that are believed to have long-term significance for cloud storage.

John C. Mace et.al [12] have proposed an automated dynamic and policy-driven approach to choose where to run workflow instances and store data while providing audit data to verify policy compliance and avoid prosecution. They also suggest an automated tool to quantify information security policy implications to help policy-makers form more justifiable and financially beneficial security policy decisions.

Mehmet Yilidiz *et al.* proposed a dynamic security model for cloud security. This model is based on eight aspects and includes four layers. Network, Storage, Servers and Application layers. It includes one enterprise level principles at the highest level and a system management aspect. It also includes two kinds of dynamic security types: horizontal and vertical. The horizontal type is specific to each layer end to end. Here, horizontal dynamic security policy for storage does only cover the security objects related to storage. The vertical type is designed to cover the interfaces between layers. Some security objects between servers and storage may be belonging to each layer. The vertical dynamic policies ensure that any common object or exception is covered. [13]

3. EXISTING ALGORITHMS FOR CLOUD SECURITY

To provide secure communication over distributed and connected resources, encryption algorithm [14] plays a vital role. It is the fundamental tool for protecting the data. Encryption algorithm converts the data into scrambled form by using "the key" and only user have the key to decrypt the data. In Symmetric key encryption, only one key is used to encrypt and decrypt the data. Another technique is known as asymmetric key encryption where two keys- private and public keys are used. Public key is used for encryption and private key is used for decryption [5]. There are a number of existing techniques used to implement security in cloud storage. Some of the existing encryption algorithms which were implemented in research work are as follows:

3.1 Data Encryption Standard (DES):- The most common SKC scheme used today, DES was designed by IBM in the 1970s and adopted by the National Bureau of

Standards (NBS) [now the National Institute for Standards and Technology (NIST)] in 1977 for commercial and unclassified government applications. DES is a block-cipher employing a 56-bit key that operates on 64-bit blocks. DES has a complex set of rules and transformations that were designed specifically to yield fast hardware implementations and slow software implementations, although this latter point is becoming less significant today since the speed of computer processors is several orders of magnitude faster today than twenty years ago. IBM also proposed a 112-bit key for DES, which was rejected at the time by the government; the use of 112-bit keys was considered in the 1990s, however, conversion was never seriously considered. DES is defined in American National Standard X3.92 and three Federal Information Processing Standards (FIPS):

- FIPS 46-3: DES
- FIPS 74: Guidelines for Implementing and Using the NBS Data Encryption Standard
- FIPS 81: DES Modes of Operation Information about vulnerabilities of DES can be obtained from the Foundation. Two important variants that strengthen DES are:
 - Triple-DES (3DES):- A variant of DES that employs up to three 56-bit keys and makes three encryption/decryption passes over the block; 3DES is also described in FIPS 46-3 and is the recommended replacement to DES.
 - DESX: A variant devised by Ron Rivest. By combining 64 additional key bits to the plaintext prior to encryption, effectively increases the key length to 120 bits.

3.2 Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) :- In 1997, NIST initiated a very public, 4-1/2 year process to develop a new secure cryptosystem for U.S. government applications. The result, the Advanced Encryption Standard, became the official successor to DES in December 2001. AES uses an SKC scheme called Rijndael, a block cipher designed by Belgian cryptographers Joan Daemen and Vincent Rijmen. The algorithm can use a variable block length and key length; the latest specification allowed any combination of keys lengths of 128, 192, or 256 bits and blocks of length 128, 192, or 256 bits. NIST initially selected Rijndael in October 2000 and formal adoption as the AES standard came in December 2001. FIPS PUB 197 describes a 128-bit block cipher employing a 128-, 192-, or 256-bit key.

3.3 Blowfish :- A symmetric 64-bit block cipher invented by Bruce Schneier; optimized for 32-bit processors with large data caches, it is significantly faster than DES on a Pentium/PowerPC-class machine. Key lengths can vary from 32 to 448 bits in length. Blowfish, available freely and intended as a substitute for DES or IDEA, is in use in a large number of products.

3.4 Twofish :- A 128-bit block cipher using 128-, 192-, or 256-bit keys. Designed to be highly secure and highly flexible, well-suited for large microprocessors, 8-bit smart card microprocessors, and dedicated hardware. Designed by a team led by Bruce Schneier and was one of the Round 2 algorithms in the AES process.

3.5 RSA :- The first, and still most common, PKC implementation, named for the three MIT mathematicians who developed it — Ronald Rivest, Adi Shamir, and Leonard Adleman. RSA today is used in hundreds of software products and can be used for key exchange, digital signatures, or encryption of small blocks of data. RSA uses a variable size encryption block and a variable size key. The key-pair is derived from a very large number, n , that is the product of two prime numbers chosen according to special rules; these primes may be 100 or more digits in length each, yielding an n with roughly twice as many digits as the prime factors. The public key information includes n and a derivative of one of the factors of n ; an attacker cannot determine the prime factors of n (and, therefore, the private key) from this information alone and that is what makes the RSA algorithm so secure. (Some descriptions of PKC erroneously state that RSA's safety is due to the difficulty in *factoring* large prime numbers. In fact, large prime numbers, like small prime numbers, only have two factors!) The ability for computers to factor large numbers, and therefore attack schemes such as RSA, is rapidly improving and systems today can find the prime factors of numbers with more than 200 digits. Nevertheless, if a large number is created from two prime factors that are roughly the same size, there is no known factorization algorithm that will solve the problem in a reasonable amount of time; a 2005 test to factor a 200-digit number took 1.5 years and over 50 years of compute time (see the Wikipedia article on integer factorization.) Regardless, one presumed protection of RSA is that users can easily increase the key size to always stay ahead of the computer processing curve. As an aside, the patent for RSA expired in September 2000 which does not appear to have affected RSA's popularity one way or the other.

3.6 Diffie-Hellman :- After the RSA algorithm was published, Diffie and Hellman came up with their own algorithm. D-H is used for secret-key key exchange only, and not for authentication or digital signatures.

3.7 Digital Signature Algorithm (DSA) :- The algorithm specified in NIST's Digital Signature Standard (DSS), provides digital signature capability for the authentication of messages.

Figure 1:- Symmetric Encryption-Decryption

Figure 2: Asymmetric Encryption- Decryption

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Nowadays Cyber Criminals can easily access data storage. In Personal Cloud Storage important data, files and records are entrusted to a third party, which enables Data Security to become the main security issue in Cloud Computing. In Cloud Storage any organization's or individual's data is stored in and accessible from multiple distributed and connected resources that comprise a cloud. To provide secure communication over distributed and connected resources authentication of stored data becomes a mandatory task. The proposed system algorithm is based on two level of encryption technique using enhanced XOR and RSA Algorithm. The algorithm for XOR and RSA are as:

4.1 XOR

In cryptography, the simple XOR cipher is a type of additive cipher, an encryption algorithm that operates according to the principles:

$$A \oplus 0 = A,$$

$$A \oplus A = 0,$$

$$(A \oplus B) \oplus C = A \oplus (B \oplus C),$$

$$(B \oplus A) \oplus A = B \oplus 0 = B,$$

where \oplus denotes the exclusive disjunction (XOR) operation. This operation is sometimes called modulus 2 addition (or subtraction, which is identical). With this logic, a string of text can be encrypted by applying the bitwise XOR operator to every character using a given

key. To decrypt the output, merely reapplying the XOR function with the key will remove the cipher.

4.2 RSA

- Step1. Choose two different large random prime numbers p and q
- Step 2. Calculate $n=p*q$ (where n is the modulus for the public key and the private keys)
- Step 3. Calculate the totient: $\Phi(n) = (p-1)*(q-1)$
- Step 4. Choose an integer e such that $1 < e < \Phi(n)$ and e is co prime to $\Phi(n)$
i.e.: e and $\Phi(n)$ share no factors other than 1; $\gcd(e, \Phi(n)) = 1$.
 e is released as the public key exponent
- Step 5. Compute d to satisfy the congruence relation $de=1 \pmod{\Phi(n)}$
i.e.: $de=1+k \Phi(n)$ for some integer k . d is kept as the private key exponent

The **public key** is made of the modulus n and the public (or encryption) exponent e .

The **private key** is made of the modulus n and the private (or decryption) exponent d which must be kept secret.

For encryption:

$$C=P^e \pmod n$$

For decryption

$$P= C^d \pmod n$$

where P is plain text, C is cipher text

4.3 Proposed Algorithm-Encryption: - In the proposed algorithm an enhanced XOR is combined with RSA to provide more secured algorithm. In the proposed algorithm the two level encryption are given as below.

4.3.1 First Level of encryption using enhanced XOR operation

- Step1. Enter plain text
- Step 2. Get the ASCII code for the character entered in the plain Text
- Step 3. Convert the ASCII to binary number
- Step 4. Select any randomized prime number (key)
- Step 5. Do exclusive OR (XOR) on step 3 and step 4
- Step 6. Convert the result of step 5 into decimal number.
A cipher text in decimal number obtained

4.3.2 Second Level of encryption

Step- Perform RSA on the output of first level Encryption

4.4 Proposed Algorithm-Decryption :- In the proposed algorithm two level decryption are given as below

4.4.1 First Level decryption

- Step1-Read cipher Text from the database

Step2- Perform RSA algorithm for first level decryption

4.4.2 Second Level Decryption

- Step1. Convert the number obtained in level 1 to binary number
- Step2. Do exclusive OR (XOR) on step 1 and randomized prime number (key)
- Step3. Convert the binary number to Decimal (which will be ASCII number)
- Step4. Convert the ASCII code to the corresponding character
- Step5. Now the plain text will be displayed to the end-user

In Our proposed System, implementation of the XOR algorithm takes place to generate first level encryption. And then we apply the RSA algorithm on the encrypted output of XOR algorithm to generate second level encryption. And same process takes place for decryption using inverse RSA and XOR algorithms. Means we applied multilevel Encryption and Decryption to provide security for cloud storage data. The proposed algorithm will be more secured compared to the single level algorithm.

5. CONCLUSION

As our proposed algorithm is a Multilevel Encryption and Decryption algorithm. Thus, in our proposed work, only the authorized user can access the data. Even if some intruder (unauthorized user) gets the data accidentally or intentionally, he must have to decrypt the data at each level which is a very difficult task without a valid key. It is expected that using multilevel encryption will provide more security for Cloud Storage than using single level encryption.

Large number of cryptography algorithms exists in the present scenario. Those algorithms work efficiently but the same type of plain text is converted into cipher text. This is the major drawback of the existing system. The proposed algorithm in this paper is given as solution for the existing problem. This algorithm converts the same type text into different type of cipher text and works very smoothly for large amount of data using dual cryptography system.

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